

CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE FORMATION OF A CULTURAL WORLDVIEW AMONG FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF A REFLECTIVE APPROACH

Kholbotaeva D.

Basic doctoral student of UzSRIPS

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Abstract. *The given article provides information regarding the content and essence of the formation of a cultural worldview among future teachers on the basis of a reflexive approach. The explanation is provided to future teachers regarding the importance of a reflexive approach in the formation of a cultural worldview in terms of actuality of reflective skills for future teachers. This article provides information on the basis of cultural studies.*

Keywords: *cultural studies, reflexive approach, cultural worldview, reflexive skills, critical thinking, creative thinking, future teacher, innovative.*

In the fast-developing current period having cultural studies skills for teachers has a great importance. It is possible to form an attitude towards oneself as a result of the development of pedagogical reflection at the required level among future teachers. As a result of the lack of reflection, future teachers cannot adequately assess their capabilities and level of development. This prevents future teachers from realizing the essence of their skills. Due to these, future teachers cannot adequately assess the mental processes of others, especially students. With the help of reflection, the teacher must determine the level of mental development of the student, the gap in this direction and clearly define the trajectory of his development.

It should be noted that the main object of cultural studies and humanitarian pedagogy is the personality of the teacher and student. That is why cultural studies directs pedagogy towards the use of mechanisms for improving personal activity. As a result, future teachers will develop sociocultural qualities, inner strength, human feelings and work as professionals with a developed cultural outlook. Such teachers can clearly demonstrate themselves in social and professional activities.

The basis of cultural studies is a human and his activities. That is why cultural studies investigates spiritual and cultural appearance and characteristics of a person. That is why cultural examples have a cultural and aesthetic impact on a person and enrich his spiritual world. As a result, a person begins to realize his personality. That is why the development of future teacher's worldview involves the joint use of not only pedagogy, but also psychology, cultural studies, and sociology. Because cultural studies, in addition to being a specific field of science, also serves to increase human spirituality as an educational subject. In today's globalized world, cultural patterns are changing rapidly. Therefore, cultural studies does not have its own clear boundaries, approaches and descriptions. The culturological approach is widely used by all humanitarian sciences, including pedagogy, but it should be emphasized that, no matter how much Uzbek culture has a cultural heritage, there are gaps in the cultural worldview of teachers, especially future teachers. For developing the cultural worldview of future teachers, it is desirable first of all to identify the sources that serve this purpose. The need to form a cultural worldview among future teachers has a number of reasons and grounds:

- identify resources that serve the development of the cultural worldview of future teachers and develop mechanisms for their use in the educational process. As a result, future teachers will be able to gain knowledge about cultural resources and methods of their use in teaching practice;

- determine the possibilities of cultural resources in the development of professional and pedagogical activities of future teachers;

- identification and selection of cultural and historical experience that serves the development of the professional cultural worldview of future teachers, assessment of the possibilities for the development of their pedagogical culture:

- for example, equipping future teachers to use cultural resources to develop students' cultural awareness.

Definitely, cultural values have always served the development of any society. The educational process aimed at developing the cultural diversity of a young teacher must have its own content and components. Students' activities are aimed at mastering cultural knowledge. This is the reason of a special attention that is being paid in terms of defining educational content that serves to develop the cultural diversity of future teachers. The content of education, aimed at developing the cultural worldview of future teachers, is focused, first of all, on the rich cultural heritage of Uzbek people. Because this knowledge is of paramount importance in the development of human cultural diversity. The content of education, aimed at developing the cultural worldview of future teachers, is determined on the basis of ensuring that students communicate with universal human and national-cultural resources. Because cultural resources serve to form and determine the personal and professional qualities of the future teacher. The cultural identity of the future teacher is determined by his communication and relationships with students.

In pedagogy, three levels of determining the content of education are theoretically justified:

- at the level of general theoretical ideas about the content of education;

- at the level of the academic subject;

- at the level of educational material.

It is known to everybody, that each defined level has a certain pedagogical basis at the level of general theoretical concepts. Because the educational content of the development of the cultural worldview of future teachers is reflected in the curriculum of a higher pedagogical institution. Because the curriculum includes educational subjects that can absorb cultural heritage. It involves the presentation of topics presented to students in a specific academic period. Cultural awareness is reflected in the SES and qualification requirements. At the same time, general cultural knowledge is reflected in the educational directions of future teachers and their requirements.

Certainly, the selection of knowledge aimed at developing the cultural worldview of future teachers and presenting it to students is based on certain principles. They are:

a) identifying and interpreting basic facts about culture.

It should be taken into account that every person has a need to strive for naturalness, to acquire the necessary knowledge to form a cultural identity. Although such evidence is sometimes contradictory, reliable evidence with a high degree of accuracy is accepted. This interpretation is expressed in the concept of the development of a person's cultural worldview.

This is the reason of why it is important to make fundamental distinctions between various regional differences and interpretations.

b) Diachronic and intercultural approaches.

Besides that, relations between cultures and relations based on dialogue are becoming increasingly important for the society of Uzbekistan. This is the reason of a special importance for future teachers to have cultural awareness and knowledge and to be able to successfully convey this knowledge to students in their future teaching activities. Only after achieving these skills then will intercultural dialogue be able to produce positive results. With the help of knowledge provided by the teacher, students gain experience of a tolerant attitude towards different cultures. They take their positive sides upon themselves. In order to form in students a correct understanding of intercultural dialogue, the teacher's worldview must occupy a strong place in his knowledge. At the same time, it is ensured that knowledge about culture acquires special significance for the historical period. As a result, the behavior, religious beliefs, arts and culture of members of society will change. Marginality in the cultural worldview of young people will be eliminated. Recognizing the differences between different cultures requires relying on the principle of intercultural communication. As a result of the development of a cultural worldview, future teachers develop the competencies of understanding and tolerant attitude towards other cultures. The principle of intercultural communication also applies to the level of evidence. This approach is reflected in the text of historical works. This approach is expressed primarily in the texts of cultural works and examples of art.

Definitely, for future teachers firstly reading the text of the works and drawing conclusions are recommended. Our observations show that in most cases, students are limited to the text included in the textbook. The texts accompanying the textbook are essentially a reference guide. In order to regularly enrich their cultural worldview, students should read and study works devoted to the historical past and present of Uzbek people and other peoples with a special culture, and draw objective conclusions about them. In the process of reading a work of fiction, future teachers need to be able to analyze its text in chronological order and interpret it structurally. In the process of forming the cultural worldview of future teachers, teaching their interpretations is of particular importance. Interpretive skills help students fully understand the essence of cultural reality expressed in a work of art and its main ideas.

The interpretation performed makes it possible to study and analyze cultural, religious, psychoanalytic and ethnological data. The principle of teaching, methods of assessment and selection of students. Within the framework of this principle, activities are carried out to understand the difference between objective reality and evaluative activity. Of particular importance is the formation of objective reality and an evaluative attitude towards it among future teachers. Without such activities, they will not have the opportunity to develop their cultural worldview. Because as a result of its correct assessment, cultural reality penetrates the consciousness of a person and serves the development of his cultural abilities.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the future teacher must have the ability to independently evaluate and select cultural phenomena. In the process of assessing any cultural phenomenon, there are many different possibilities associated with its assessment. In this process, many different area assessment tools must be introduced to achieve a proper assessment of cultural phenomena. Such mechanisms include criteria for assessing a cultural event, measures, evidence, their comparison and reflection. Future teachers must have the ability to form their own point of view, argue and defend it, which directly depends on the level of development of their cultural worldview.

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